

The effect of compression on the morphological and electrical properties of semiconducting nanosheet networks

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ABSTRACT

Solution-processed networks of two-dimensional (2D) semiconducting nanosheets are promising for flexible and printed electronics but often suffer from limited electrical properties due to poor inter-nanosheet charge transport. We examine how uniaxial mechanical compression alters the morphology and electrical properties of networks made from liquid-phase-exfoliated WS₂ nanosheets of varying sizes. Compression reduces network thickness considerably (20-60%) and substantially smooths the surface. Three-dimensional imaging shows extensive porosity collapse and a strong decrease in tortuosity, with the most pronounced structural changes occurring in networks formed from the largest nanosheets. All networks display improved electrical conductivity after compression, the enhancement increases systematically with nanosheet size, reaching a 20-fold increase for the largest sheets. Modelling the conductivity as a function of nanosheet length indicates that the average junction resistance is largely independent of nanosheet size, both before and after compression, however, compression reduces junction resistance by roughly an order of magnitude. Temperature-dependent conductivity and impedance spectroscopy measurements further show that inter-nanosheet junctions remain point-like after compression, suggesting that the reduction in junction resistance is caused by shortening of the effective hopping distance rather than converting point-like junctions into extended planar contacts. These findings clarify the mechanisms by which mechanical compression enhances charge transport and outline its capabilities and limitations for improving the electrical properties of solution-processed 2D networks.

Keywords: 2D nanosheet networks; Liquid-phase exfoliation (LPE); Mechanical compression; Junction resistance; Charge transport; Porous network morphology; Impedance spectroscopy

INTRODUCTION

Inks containing two-dimensional (2D) nanosheets can be deposited from solution to form thin films that are commonly referred to as nanosheet networks.^{1, 2} Such networks have attracted significant attention over the past decade and are now being explored across a wide range of applications, including energy storage,^{2, 3} catalysis,⁴ bio-sensing,⁵ and flexible electronics.^{6, 7} In particular, solution-processed nanosheet networks have shown considerable promise for use in flexible and wearable electronic technologies,^{7, 8} where they have been demonstrated in devices such as thin-film transistors,⁹ photodetectors,¹⁰ light emitting diodes¹¹ and piezoresistive sensors.¹² In most of these applications, device performance is critically dependent on the electrical conductivity and carrier mobility of the nanosheet network.^{1, 13} As a result, there is substantial interest in developing strategies to maximise the electrical performance of solution-processed nanosheet assemblies and in building a deeper understanding of the physical factors that govern charge transport in these systems. Recently, it has become clear that network mobility is limited by the resistance associated with inter-nanosheet junctions in almost all cases.¹⁴ This means it would be particularly useful to develop methods to control the resistance of such junctions.

At present, the most widely studied solution-processable semiconducting nanosheets are produced using either liquid-phase exfoliation¹⁵ (LPE) or electrochemical exfoliation¹⁶ (EE). LPE is particularly attractive because it is simple, scalable, and compatible with a wide range of layered materials and solvents. However, nanosheets produced by LPE typically have relatively low aspect ratios, with modest lateral dimensions and significant thickness.¹⁷ Networks formed from such nanosheets generally exhibit low electrical conductivity and mobility, relative to the nanosheets they are composed of.¹⁸ In contrast, EE nanosheets often possess much higher aspect ratios,¹⁸ resulting in networks with mobilities approaching that of the constituent nanosheets.¹³ These improvements are commonly attributed to the alignment of nanosheets during network formation¹⁹ resulting in large area inter-nanosheet junctions.²⁰ Despite these advantages, electrochemical exfoliation methods currently yield relatively low quantities of material and are less mature from a manufacturing perspective.

While one obvious route to improved network performance is therefore, the development of scalable methods to produce large quantities of high-aspect-ratio semiconducting nanosheets, an alternative and potentially more versatile strategy is to apply post-deposition treatments to enhance the electrical properties of networks formed from low-aspect ratio LPE nanosheets. A defining feature of networks composed of LPE nanosheets is their high porosity.²¹ Because such nanosheets are relatively rigid, they tend to form jammed, highly disordered networks with inefficient packing.^{20, 21} This high porosity is accompanied by poorly defined inter-nanosheet contacts, which are generally believed to be point-like in nature and to possess very high junction resistances.²⁰ As a consequence, electrical transport in these networks is typically junction-limited,¹ causing the mobility of the network to be considerably lower than the constituent nanosheets.

These considerations suggest that mechanical compression may provide a viable route to improving the electrical performance of LPE nanosheet networks. By reducing porosity, increasing nanosheet alignment, and improving packing density, compression could, in principle, reduce the effective junction resistance and potentially even transform high resistance point-like junctions into larger-area, low resistance planar contacts. Such changes would be expected to enhance network conductivity and mobility substantially. A number of studies^{22, 23} have indeed examined the effects of compression or densification on nanosheet networks, reporting reductions in resistivity (see ref¹ for review of this topic). These works have demonstrated that compression can improve macroscopic transport properties by increasing network density, annihilating pores and enhancing nanosheet alignment. Moreover, micromechanical compression studies have demonstrated that network mechanical properties are influenced by both compression and nanosheet size, suggesting that sheet size may play a significant role on morphological changes induced by compression.^{24, 25}

However, despite this progress, the detailed impact of compression on network morphology and charge transport mechanisms in networks composed of low-aspect-ratio, LPE nanosheets, particularly semiconducting ones, remains poorly understood. Key questions remain regarding whether compression simply reduces inter-sheet spacing or whether it qualitatively modifies the nature of the junctions and so the inter-nanosheet charge transfer mechanism. Addressing these questions requires a combined structural and electrical analysis capable of linking nanoscale morphology to macroscopic transport behaviour.

In this work, we apply uniaxial compression to networks of LPE WS₂ nanosheets, achieving thickness reductions of up to 60%. By combining detailed morphological characterisation, DC

electrical measurements, and impedance spectroscopy, we systematically investigate how compression modifies network structure and charge transport. We show that compression leads to substantial increases in network conductivity, driven primarily by a large reduction in junction resistance, although the fundamental transport mechanism remains junction-limited and thermally activated. Importantly, our results demonstrate that although compression brings nanosheets closer together, the junctions remain effectively point-like, providing new insight into the limits of mechanical densification as a strategy for enhancing charge transport in solution-processed nanosheet networks.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Nanosheet production and characterisation

Tungsten disulfide (WS_2) nanosheets were produced by LPE, and the resulting stock dispersion was size-selected into ten fractions using liquid cascade centrifugation (LCC).^{26, 27} LCC comprises multiple centrifugation steps, each performed at progressively higher rotation rates (expressed by the rotor angular frequency, ω , or rpm). At each step, a sediment enriched in nanosheets within a particular size range is collected. The sediments can then be redispersed in solvent to yield size-selected inks.

Optical extinction spectra were collected for each size-selected ink, as shown in Figure 1A. The shape of the spectra varies significantly across the fractions. This behaviour is consistent with changes in both light absorption and scattering as nanosheet length and thickness increases, in agreement with previous observations.^{26, 28} Qualitatively, the spectra indicate that the nanosheet size decreases as the rotation speed increases across successive centrifugation steps. Raman spectra were acquired for nanosheets extracted from each fraction. In all cases, the spectra were very similar. The inset in Figure 1A shows a typical Raman spectrum collected for one fraction (2000 rpm, 209 rad/s), displaying the A_{1g} and E_{2g} modes expected for 2H- WS_2 .

After drop-casting nanosheets onto SiO_2 substrates, atomic force microscopy (AFM) was used to measure the distributions of nanosheet lengths and thicknesses for a subset of six fractions. Example histograms of nanosheet length and thickness for the 2000 rpm fraction are shown in Figures 1B and 1C. From these histograms, we extract the mean nanosheet length, l_{NS} , and thickness, t_{NS} , for a subset of the size-selected fraction.

Before analysing these results in detail, it is important to assess whether the AFM data are consistent with theoretical predictions for LCC.²⁷ It has recently been shown that the product

of the mean nanosheet length and thickness should scale with the inverse square of the rotation speed used to collect each sediment: $l_{NS} \times t_{NS} \propto \omega^{-2}$.²⁷ Using our AFM measurements, we test this prediction in Figure 1D and find good linearity, confirming that the data are consistent with centrifugation theory.

In addition, a simple model of the LPE process predicts that the mean nanosheet length scales as a power law of the mean nanosheet thickness (assuming nanosheet length and width are linearly connected): $l_{NS} \propto t_{NS}^{\beta/2}$.¹⁷ This prediction is tested in Figure 1E, where we find good agreement with an exponent of $\beta/2 = 1.44$, indicating $\beta = 2.88$, which shows excellent agreement with previously measured values ($\beta = 2.89$)¹⁷. This further confirms that the AFM data are consistent with expectations for nanosheets produced by LPE.

When these relations hold (as verified in Figures 1D and 1E), the mean nanosheet length and thickness should each scale with rotation rate in a well-defined manner: $l_{NS} \propto \omega^{-(1+\alpha)}$ and $t_{NS} \propto \omega^{-(1-\alpha)}$, where $\alpha = (\beta - 2) / (\beta + 2)$.²⁷ Using the value $\beta = 2.88$ extracted from Figure 1E, we obtain $\alpha = 0.18$. As shown in Figures 1F and 1G, both nanosheet length and thickness vary with rotation rate in a manner consistent with these predictions.

By fitting these datasets, we obtain quantitative relationships between both nanosheet length and thickness and the rotation rate (see SI). As shown in Table S1, these relationships enable us to calculate accurate values of nanosheet dimensions from the rotation rate used in centrifugation for all fractions, including those not directly measured by AFM. Because we combine all measured data with a theoretical model, we expect these calculated values to have reduced error and scatter compared to standard AFM data. Using this method, we find that our ten fractions have nanosheet lengths and thicknesses ranging from 788 nm and 14.9 nm respectively for the largest nanosheets, to 51 nm and 2.5 nm for the smallest nanosheets. The nanosheet aspect ratios (which we define as l_{NS}/t_{NS}) vary from 53 for the largest nanosheets to 21 for the smallest nanosheets. These values are roughly consistent with expectations for tungsten disulfide nanosheets made by LPE.¹⁷

Compressing networks

For each size-selected fraction, nanosheet networks were spray-deposited onto PET substrates pre-patterned with gold interdigitated electrode arrays. The as-deposited network thicknesses were on the order of a few micrometres. Figure 2A shows top-down and cross-sectional SEM images of an uncompressed network prepared from the 2000 rpm nanosheet fraction. The

network appears highly disordered and contains significant porosity, features that are typical of solution-deposited nanosheet networks produced by LPE.^{20, 21, 29}

The networks were subsequently compressed uniaxially in a hydraulic load cell at 200 MPa and held for 60 s at room temperature. The pressure ramp time was ~5-10 s (loading rate was ~20-40 MPa/s). At this relatively high rate, we expect the nanosheets not to have time to move appreciably (creep) and so the response to applied stress is expected to be predominately via nanosheet bending. Preliminary measurements showed little variation in the properties of the compressed network with compression time. However, the change in electrical properties after compression did increase significantly with pressure (see SI). The largest increase was observed for a pressure of 200 MPa – we consistently used this pressure thereafter. In the future, it will be interesting to study in more detail how the details of the compression process affect the electrical properties. As indicated above, the compression rate is likely to have a significant effect.

Figure 2B presents top-down and cross-sectional SEM images of the same network after compression. These images show a clear increase in nanosheet alignment, together with a dramatic reduction in network porosity. This indicates that compression effectively annihilates pores, consistent with previous observations.²²

By measuring the film thickness before and after compression, we calculate the compression ratio, defined as $(t_f - t_i) / t_i$ where t_i and t_f are the initial and final network thicknesses, respectively. The compression ratios are plotted as a function of nanosheet length in Figure 2C. With the exception of the smallest nanosheet fraction, which appears to be an outlier, the compression ratio increases with nanosheet size, reaching approximately 0.5–0.6 for the largest nanosheets. We explore the effect of compression on the structure of the size-selected networks in detail below.

Figure 2D summarizes the change in the Raman A_{1g} mode position for networks composed of WS_2 nanosheets with progressively increasing nanosheet length, before and after compression. A clear shift of the A_{1g} band to higher frequency is observed after compression for all WS_2 networks, indicating that the Raman response of WS_2 is sensitive to the applied compressive stress. The A_{1g} mode in WS_2 is known to be strain-sensitive, with the magnitude of the band shift proportional to the applied strain.³⁰ Figure 2D shows that the magnitude of the A_{1g} shift increases with nanosheet length, reaching a maximum for networks with $l_{NS} \approx 300-600$ nm, before decreasing markedly when l_{NS} approaches ~800 nm. From this result we infer that inter-

nanosheet stress transfer within networks formed from larger nanosheets is more effective than in networks of smaller nanosheets. This interpretation is consistent with reports on 2D-materials-based composites, where nanosheets must exceed a critical length to enable efficient stress transfer.³¹ The reduced shift observed for networks with ~ 800 nm nanosheets may be attributed to their significantly greater thickness and to additional attenuation of interlayer stress transfer within the thicker nanosheets during compression.

Network morphology

To quantitatively compare the changes in network structure before and after uniaxial compression we employed nanotomography-based 3D imaging.²¹ FIB-SEM nanotomography (FIB-SEM nt) was used to sequentially mill and image a stack of high-resolution network cross-sections, such as the uncompressed and compressed WS₂ networks shown in Figure 2A-B. As previously demonstrated,²¹ each image in a stack can be segmented into its discrete nanosheet and pore contributions and stitched together to produce high-resolution 3D images. Volumetric reconstructions of the same WS₂ nanosheet network ($l_{NS} = 170$ nm) are shown both before and after uniaxial compression in Figures 3A-B with a voxel size of $5 \times 5 \times 15$ nm.

Such images allow for quantification of network morphology using parameters such as the porosity, P_{Net} , and the tortuosity factor of the nanosheet network, κ_{Net} . Here, P_{Net} represents the fractional pore volume contained within the nanosheet network, while κ_{Net} is an effective metric for the nanosheet connectivity by measuring how tortuous a path through the network is in a given direction due to the presence of pores.^{32, 33} A tortuosity factor of $\kappa_{Net} = 1$ represents a straight-line path through the nanosheet network in the in-plane direction, while values of $\kappa_{Net} > 1$ represent longer paths, driven by convolutions in the network structure. The uncompressed WS₂ network (Figure 3A) exhibits considerable porosity and poor connectivity, as reflected by values of $P_{Net} = 39$ % and $\kappa_{Net} = 1.43$, in agreement with reported values for spray-deposited LPE nanosheet networks.²¹ However, following uniaxial compression (Figure 3B) we observe an 88% decrease in the network porosity ($P_{Net} = 5$ %), with the pore annihilation and network densification leading to a network tortuosity factor of $\kappa_{Net} = 1.07$, approaching the idealised value of $\kappa_{Net} = 1$. This porosity value significantly improves upon published values for uncompressed sprayed-deposited LPE nanosheet networks (~ 30 – 55 %),^{18, 21, 34} and approaches P_{Net} values reported for highly aligned networks of high aspect ratio EE nanosheets of ~ 2 – 5 %.^{9, 20} Such reductions in P_{Net} and improvements in nanosheet connectivity would be expected to alter the nature of the inter-nanosheet contacts and reduce R_j , leading to an enhancement of charge transport through the network. Similarly, the visible reduction in the surface roughness

of the network following compression (Figure 3B) would be expected to improve interfacial quality in printed heterostack devices. We note that network stiffness increases with compressive strain,²⁴ such that as pores become progressively harder to collapse. This means it will be difficult to reduce porosity below our lowest value (5%).

To determine the influence of nanosheet size during the compression process, we 3D imaged a subset (i.e. those labelled XL(L), 2k and 6k in Table S1) of the size-selected WS₂ networks before and after compression. The root mean square network roughness, S_q , tortuosity factor, and porosity are plotted as a function of nanosheet size, l_{NS} , in each network before and after compression in Figures 3C-E. In all cases, we observe decreases in the network roughness, porosity and tortuosity factor following compression, highlighting the general applicability of compression in improving network structure. However, the magnitude of these changes in network morphology also exhibit a clear dependence on nanosheet size, with the largest relative improvements in S_q , κ_{Net} and P_{Net} observed for networks of larger WS₂ nanosheets in Figures 3C-E. For example, for the largest nanosheets, we see S_q decreasing from ~ 250 nm to ~ 100 nm; κ_{Net} decreasing from ~ 2.2 to ~ 1.2 ; and P_{Net} decreasing from $\sim 55\%$ to $\sim 20\%$.

As shown in Fig 1, nanosheet length and thickness are intrinsically coupled for LPE nanosheets.¹⁷ Thus, we expect networks comprised of nanosheets with larger l_{NS} to also have larger nanosheet thicknesses, t_{NS} . The increased rigidity of larger LPE nanosheets leads to jammed packing and increased P_{Net} values when compared to thinner nanosheets (Figure 3E). However, under uniaxial compression, these pores are annihilated, and the networks homogenise, leading to a weaker dependence of porosity on nanosheet size. We see greater reductions in both tortuosity and roughness for those networks with larger nanosheets. This observation is in line with expectation: as nanosheet size increases, network stiffness decreases,²⁵ making it easier to induce plastic deformation.

To show this, we plot a morphological scaling factor^{14, 21} described by $\alpha = (1 - P_{Net}) / \kappa_{Net}$, versus nanosheet length in Figure 3F, before and after compression. This factor has been used to scale electrical conductivity in nanosheet films by accounting for the presence of pores and convoluted current paths through the network. A value of $\alpha = 1$ suggests that charge transport through the film is unhindered by network morphology, while scaling factors of $\alpha < 1$ reflect reduced charge transport efficiency driven by morphological constraints. As shown in Figure 3F, networks of smaller nanosheets consistently demonstrate larger values for α . However, following compression, the calculated values for α improve significantly for each network,

rising from $\alpha \sim 0.2 - 0.6$ to $\alpha \sim 0.8 - 0.9$, with the largest improvements again arising in networks of larger nanosheets. In both cases, α exhibits a well-defined power law dependence on l_{NS} , with the exponent decreasing from -0.39 to -0.11 after compression. This demonstrates that while a dependence on l_{NS} still exists, that compression has reduced the influence of nanosheet size and significantly improved the network connectivity, which should lead to an improvement in network electrical properties.

Network DC electrical properties

Using the pre-patterned interdigitated electrode arrays, the conductivity of the nanosheet networks was measured before and after compression. The measured conductivities are plotted as a function of nanosheet length in Figure 4A. Prior to compression, the network conductivity ranged from approximately 3×10^{-5} to 10^{-3} S m⁻¹, exhibiting a well-defined maximum at a nanosheet length of roughly 300 nm. This behaviour is consistent with previous observations of the electrical properties of LPE WS₂ networks.¹⁴ After compression, however, we observe a clear increase in conductivity for all nanosheet lengths, with conductivities ranging from approximately 2×10^{-4} to 10^{-2} S m⁻¹. A weak peak remains, now centred at a nanosheet length of approximately 400 nm.

To quantify the effect of compression, we calculated the ratio of the conductivity of the compressed network to that of the uncompressed network. This ratio is plotted versus nanosheet length in Figure 4B. As with the compression ratio data in Figure 2C, the smallest nanosheet fraction appears to be an outlier. Excluding this point, the conductivity ratio increases systematically with nanosheet length. This indicates that compression has a greater impact on network connectivity in networks composed of larger nanosheets, consistent with the trends observed in Figure 2C and Figures 3D-F, where compression is more effective at reducing porosity for larger nanosheets.

It is possible to quantitatively analyze the conductivity data before and after compression, in order to gain a better understanding of how it affects the network electrical properties. To do this, we utilize a recently published model for the electrical properties of nanosheet networks:¹⁴

$$\sigma_{Net} \approx \frac{n_{NS} e \mu_{NS} (1 - P_{Net}) / \kappa_{Net}}{\left[1 + 2R_J n_{NS} e \mu_{NS} t_{NS} \right] \left[1 + \frac{2}{t_{NS} l_{NS}^2 n_{NS}} \right]} \quad (1)$$

Here σ_{Net} is the conductivity of the network, R_j is the resistance of the inter-nanosheet junctions while μ_{NS} and n_{NS} are the mobility and carrier density of the nanosheets themselves. All other parameters are as previously defined.

In order to apply this equation, we need to make two modifications. Ideally, we would plot the network conductivity versus either the nanosheet length or thickness and fit the data using this equation. However, this equation contains both nanosheet length and thickness with both values varying over the set of fractions. To get around this, we note that the fit in Figure 1E shows a well-defined relationship between l_{NS} and t_{NS} , consistent with $t_{\text{NS}} = 2.79 \times 10^{-4} l_{\text{NS}}^{0.70}$. Thus, when fitting, we will replace t_{NS} in Equation 1 with this expression, leaving only the l_{NS} -dependence.

Secondly, Equation 1 includes the morphological parameter $\alpha = (1 - P_{\text{Net}}) / \kappa_{\text{Net}}$, reported in Figure 3F. The influence of this parameter must be accounted for during fitting. As shown in Figure 3F, we have already obtained an approximate empirical relationship between α and nanosheet length, l_{NS} . Therefore, the simplest way to account for nanosheet-length-dependent morphology is to normalize the conductivity at each nanosheet length by the corresponding value of α calculated from this empirical relationship. This allows us to plot $\sigma_{\text{Net}}/\alpha$ for the networks before and after compression, as shown in Figures 4C and 4D. These normalized curves can then be fitted using a modified version of Equation 1, in which we also eliminate t_{NS} as described above:

$$\frac{\sigma_{\text{Net}} \kappa_{\text{Net}}}{(1 - P_{\text{Net}})} \approx \frac{n_{\text{NS}} e \mu_{\text{NS}}}{\left[1 + R_j n_{\text{NS}} e \mu_{\text{NS}} \times 5.58 \times 10^{-4} l_{\text{NS}}^{0.7}\right] \left[1 + \frac{1}{1.4 \times 10^{-4} l_{\text{NS}}^{2.7} n_{\text{NS}}}\right]} \quad (2)$$

Even after removing the explicit morphological dependence, this expression still contains three fitting parameters, R_j , n_{NS} and μ_{NS} which made it difficult to obtain reliable fits. To improve fitting robustness for both data sets, we performed various fits, in each case fixing the nanosheet mobility at values between 10 and 200 $\text{cm}^2 \text{V}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$ (see SI). This resulted in substantially more reliable fitting, with much lower fitting errors for R_j and n_{NS} . For the data before compression, we found R_j , n_{NS} and fit quality to show limited variation with the fixed value of μ_{NS} used in the fit (see SI). Taking the values obtained using $\mu_{\text{NS}} = 60 \text{ cm}^2/\text{Vs}$, the previously reported mobility for LPE WS_2 nanosheets, gives: $R_j = 9.7 \pm 2.3 \text{ G}\Omega$ and $n_{\text{NS}} = (2.0$

$\pm 0.6) \times 10^{21} \text{ m}^{-3}$ before compression. Combining these values for μ_{NS} and n_{NS} yields a value $\sigma_{\text{NS}} = 1.9 \pm 0.6 \text{ S/m}$ for the conductivity of the nanosheets within the network.

However, for the data after compression, R_{J} , n_{NS} and fit quality did show some dependence on the fixed value of μ_{NS} used in the fit (see SI). The best fit quality was found at $\mu_{\text{NS}} \sim 100 \text{ cm}^2/\text{Vs}$. Reporting the fit parameters at this mobility value gives $R_{\text{J}} = 0.86 \pm 0.29 \text{ G}\Omega$ and $n_{\text{NS}} = (0.34 \pm 0.09) \times 10^{21} \text{ m}^{-3}$ after compression.

We first consider the calculated values for junction resistance. The pre-compression value is consistent with previous reports for as-produced networks of semiconducting nanosheets prepared by LPE.¹⁴ After compression, we observe an approximately tenfold reduction in junction resistance, which contributes substantially to the conductivity increase upon compression. Importantly, the fact that both datasets can be fitted using a single junction resistance value (one for the uncompressed case and one for the compressed case) implies that the junction resistance is independent of, or only weakly dependent on, nanosheet size. Size-independent junction resistances are commonly observed in networks of low-aspect-ratio nanosheets, such as those produced by LPE.¹⁴

However, we have previously observed size-dependent junction resistance in networks of EE nanosheets.²⁰ This difference is thought to arise from variations in nanosheet aspect ratio and flexibility. Low-aspect-ratio nanosheets are relatively rigid and tend to form jammed networks with effectively point-like junctions. In contrast, high-aspect-ratio nanosheets are more flexible and can align more readily with neighbouring sheets, resulting in conformal junctions in which the junction resistance scales inversely with the junction area. The fact that our data - both before and after compression - are consistent with a single junction resistance value strongly suggests that junctions remain point-like in both cases. Thus, while compression reduces the junction resistance, it does not appear to produce large area junctions.

This conclusion is also supported by the absolute magnitude of the junction resistance after compression. Even after compression, the junction resistance remains on the order of $\text{G}\Omega$, which is much larger than typical values for semiconducting nanosheets forming large-area junctions, where junction resistances are more commonly on the order of $\text{M}\Omega$.^{14, 35}

We now turn to the carrier density values extracted from the fits. Our data implies an approximately sixfold reduction in carrier density upon compression. While this trend is not central to the present work, it warrants discussion because mechanical deformation in 2D semiconductors is widely known to modify electronic structure and transport, and strain can

influence charge distribution and carrier behaviour.³⁶ One plausible explanation is compression-driven de-doping: pore annihilation and densification may expel trapped water/oxygen/residual solvent or reduce internal surface accessibility, removing adsorbate-induced charge transfer that can contribute to carrier density in highly porous, high-surface-area networks.³⁷ In addition, increased packing may enhance dielectric screening and promote carrier trapping/localization at strained junctions, reducing the effective mobile carrier density extracted from a junction-dominated transport model, even as junction resistance falls. Future work will involve independent probes of doping and carrier density (e.g., Seebeck measurements, gated transport, or spectroscopic doping metrics) to determine whether compression causes true de-doping or mainly increases carrier localization/trapping.

The data discussed above are consistent with the internal sheet junctions remaining point-like after compression, even though the junction resistance falls by roughly an order of magnitude. We can investigate this the cause of the decrease in junction resistance using temperature dependent conductivity measurements.

Although networks of semiconducting nanosheets can exhibit a range of conduction mechanisms - such as variable-range hopping at low temperature - near room temperature they typically display thermally activated behaviour, consistent with Miller–Abrahams-type hopping.^{14, 38, 39} In this regime, the conductivity is well described by:

$$\sigma_{\text{Net}} \propto \exp(-2l_J / a) \exp(-E_a / k_B T) \quad (3)$$

Where l_J is the hopping distance, a is the localisation length (a constant of the nanosheets) and E_a is the activation energy.

In general, temperature-dependent measurements provide insight into the dominant (or rate-limiting) conduction mechanism. Since the junction resistance is much larger than the nanosheet resistance, we expect the temperature dependence to be governed primarily by inter-sheet charge transfer across junctions. For networks of LPE nanosheets - where junctions are expected to be point-like - the resulting inter-nanosheet transport typically yields activation energies of around 200–500 meV.^{1, 18, 40} However, it is worth noting that this activation energy can decrease sharply under electrostatic gating.³⁸ In contrast, networks of high-aspect-ratio sheets with low-resistance, conformal junctions generally exhibit much lower activation energies, typically in the range 30–100 meV.^{14, 38, 41}

Here, we measured the network conductivity as a function of temperature near room temperature for networks before and after compression, with the aim of quantifying the effect of changing junction resistance on the activation energy. The temperature-dependent conductivity is shown in Figure 4E (as a function of temperature) and Figure 4F (as a function of inverse temperature). For both uncompressed and compressed networks, the logarithm of the conductivity scales linearly with inverse temperature, as expected for activated transport.

From the slopes of these curves, we extract activation energies of 414 meV and 392 meV for the uncompressed and compressed networks, respectively. These values are relatively high and are fully consistent with expectations for networks of LPE nanosheets with point-like junctions.^{1, 18} Importantly, we observe very little change in activation energy upon compression. This strongly suggests that the fundamental mechanism of inter-sheet charge transfer is not significantly altered by compression.

It is important to note that even a small change in activation energy can result in a significant change in conductivity. The reduction in activation energy from 414 meV to 392 meV observed for the 2krm sample correlates in an increase in exponential factor ($\exp(-E_a / k_B T)$) by $\times 2.3$. However, this is not enough to fully explain the fourfold increase in conductivity after compression observed for this sample. Referring to Equation 3, the additional conductivity increase implies that the hopping distance between nanosheets, l_j , must also decrease upon compression. Thus, our results suggest that compression both reduces the activation energy and brings nanosheets closer together - reducing the effective hopping distance - while the point-like nature of the junctions remains essentially unchanged.

Impedance spectroscopy measurements after compression

We can investigate the electrical properties of our nanosheet networks in greater detail using impedance spectroscopy. This is a powerful technique that can, in principle, be used to independently determine the resistances of both the nanosheets and the inter-nanosheet junctions within a network.¹⁴ To date, however, impedance spectroscopy has been applied almost exclusively to networks of high-aspect-ratio, EE nanosheets.^{14, 35, 42} Such networks typically exhibit relatively low junction resistances and, consequently, higher conductivities than networks formed from low-aspect-ratio, LPE nanosheets.^{14, 42} As a result, networks of LPE nanosheets have not previously been studied using impedance spectroscopy, since their high overall resistances generally place them outside the measurable range of the technique. In

the present case, however, the substantially enhanced conductivity of our compressed networks makes impedance measurements feasible.

To test this possibility, we focused on the nanosheet size that produced the highest-conductivity networks (mean nanosheet length $l_{NS}=594$ nm), as shown in Figure 4D. To further reduce the overall network resistance, we fabricated an unusually thick network, $t_{Net}=25$ μm post compression). Prior to compression, it was not possible to obtain reliable impedance spectra from these samples. After compression, however, we were able to record high-quality real and imaginary impedance spectra for samples fabricated with five different electrode separations (channel lengths) ranging from 50 to 150 μm . The measured impedance spectra are shown in Figures 5A and 5B, where Figure 5A presents the real part of the impedance and Figure 5B shows the imaginary part. As expected, the impedance increases systematically with increasing channel length.

We have previously shown that nanosheet networks can be modelled using an equivalent circuit consisting of a parallel combination of a resistance and a capacitance, in series with a second resistance, as illustrated schematically in Figure 5A.^{14, 35, 42} In this model, R_S and R_P represent the contributions to the overall network resistance from the nanosheets and the inter-nanosheet junctions, respectively. Each junction is also associated with a capacitance, and the collective effect of these junctions gives rise to a network capacitance C_P . In principle, relatively simple expressions can be derived for the real and imaginary parts of the impedance associated with this circuit. In practice, however, the presence of a distribution of junction resistances and capacitances necessitates the use of a slightly more general description:¹⁴

$$\text{Re } Z(\omega) = R_S + \frac{R_P + [1 + (\omega R_P C_P)^n \cos(n\pi / 2)]}{1 + 2(\omega R_P C_P)^n \cos(n\pi / 2) + (\omega R_P C_P)^{2n}} \quad (4)$$

$$-\text{Im } Z(\omega) = \frac{R_P (\omega R_P C_P)^n \sin(n\pi / 2)}{1 + 2(\omega R_P C_P)^n \cos(n\pi / 2) + (\omega R_P C_P)^{2n}} \quad (5)$$

Here, n is a parameter that reflects the breadth of the distribution of the junction resistance within the network.⁴³

We fitted the data in Figures 5A and 5B using these expressions, extracting R_P and C_P from fits to both the real and imaginary components of the impedance, and R_S from fits to the real component alone. The resulting values are plotted as a function of channel length, L_{Ch} , in

Figures 5C–E. These data show that both R_P and R_{NS} increase with increasing channel length, while C_P decreases with channel length, exactly as expected.

We have recently shown that these parameters are governed by the following relationships:⁴²

$$R_S = \frac{2t_{NS}\kappa_{Net}R_{NS}}{W_{Ch}t_{Net}(1-P_{Net})} \left[1 + \frac{2}{n_{NS}t_{NS}l_{NS}^2} \right] L_{Ch} + R_c \quad (6)$$

$$R_P = \frac{2t_{NS}\kappa_{Net}R_J}{W_{Ch}t_{Net}(1-P_{Net})} \left[1 + \frac{2}{n_{NS}t_{NS}l_{NS}^2} \right] L_{Ch} \quad (7)$$

$$C_P = C_J R_J / R_P = \frac{C_J W_{Ch} t_{Net} (1 - P_{Net}) / \kappa_{Net}}{2t_{NS} \left[1 + \frac{2}{n_{NS} t_{NS} l_{NS}^2} \right]} \frac{1}{L_{Ch}} \quad (8)$$

Here, t_{Net} ($= 24.5 \mu\text{m}$) is the network thickness, W_{Ch} is the channel width, and R_c is the total electrode-semiconductor contact resistance. These expressions directly link the macroscopic parameters R_S , R_P , C_P to their microscopic counterparts: the nanosheet resistance, R_{NS} , the junction resistance, R_J , and the junction capacitance, C_J . They predict that both R_P and R_{NS} scale linearly with channel length, while C_P scales inversely with channel length. We used these expressions to fit the data in Figures 5C–E, obtaining good agreement in all cases. The extracted contact resistance was relatively small, approximately 35Ω .

Using $\alpha = (1 - P_{Net}) / \kappa_{Net} = 0.71$, $t_{NS} = 13.4 \text{ nm}$, $W_{Ch} = 0.02 \text{ m}$, $l_{NS} = 594 \text{ nm}$, and $n_{NS} = 3.4 \times 10^{20} \text{ m}^{-3}$, we obtain $R_{NS} = 27.6 \pm 10 \text{ M}\Omega$, $R_J = 0.67 \pm 0.2 \text{ G}\Omega$, $C_J = (30 \pm 10) \times 10^{-18} \text{ F}$. We first note that the extracted junction resistance is very close to the value obtained independently from fitting the data in Figure 4D, providing strong validation of the impedance-based approach.

Furthermore, the nanosheet resistance obtained from impedance spectroscopy can be combined with the measured nanosheet thickness and carrier density (Figure 4D) to estimate the nanosheet mobility. This yields $\mu_{NS} = 250 \pm 175 \text{ cm}^2/\text{Vs}$. The relatively large uncertainty arises primarily from the uncertainty in the nanosheet resistance, which is further compounded by uncertainties in the other parameters. Nevertheless, this result implies a nanosheet mobility in the range $75\text{--}425 \text{ cm}^2/\text{Vs}$, which is fully consistent with the value of approximately $100 \text{ cm}^2/\text{Vs}$ inferred from the conductivity analysis above.

Finally, we note that the extracted junction capacitance is approximately two orders of magnitude smaller than values previously reported for networks of high-aspect-ratio nanosheets.^{14, 42} In earlier work, we have suggested that the junction capacitance provides a

direct measure of the junction area. On this basis, the present value of C_J corresponds to a junction area of $A_J=3400\pm 1100\text{ nm}^2$, which is much smaller than the $\sim 0.25\text{ }\mu\text{m}^2$ junction areas estimated for networks of high-aspect-ratio nanosheets. As a fraction of the nanosheet area, this value is $\sim 1\%$, trivial compared to the values of 33-40% found for high-aspect-ratio nanosheets.^{14,42} This is consistent with the picture that high-aspect-ratio nanosheets form large-area, conformal junctions, whereas the low-aspect-ratio nanosheets studied here form small, point-like junctions, in full agreement with the conclusions drawn earlier.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, we have investigated the impact of uniaxial mechanical compression on the morphology and electrical transport properties of networks of LPE WS_2 nanosheets. Compression of the initially porous networks leads to substantial increases in electrical conductivity, demonstrating that post-deposition mechanical processing can significantly enhance the performance of solution-processed 2D semiconductor networks.

Through a combination of DC transport, temperature-dependent measurements, and impedance spectroscopy, we show that the conductivity enhancement arises primarily from a large reduction in inter-nanosheet junction resistance. Importantly, the extracted activation energies remain essentially unchanged upon compression, indicating that the fundamental charge-transport mechanism is not altered. Instead, the reduced resistance is consistent with a decrease in the effective inter-nanosheet hopping distance rather than a transition from point-like to large area junctions.

Impedance spectroscopy enables quantitative separation of nanosheet and junction contributions to the network resistance and confirms that, even after compression, junctions in these low-aspect-ratio networks remain small in area. This contrasts sharply with networks formed from high-aspect-ratio nanosheets and highlights the central role of nanosheet geometry in determining junction structure and transport behaviour.

Overall, these results clarify both the capabilities and limitations of mechanical compression as a strategy for improving charge transport in solution-processed nanosheet networks. While compression effectively reduces porosity and enhances connectivity, further improvements in mobility will likely require complementary approaches such as increasing nanosheet aspect ratio or engineering inter-nanosheet contacts.

EXPERIMENTAL

Nanosheet exfoliation and size selection

WS₂ powder (Thermofisher, 99.8% (metals basis)) was exfoliated into nanosheets by liquid phase exfoliation.⁴⁴ The powder was dispersed in 2-propanol (IPA, Sigma Aldrich, HPLC grade, 99.9%) at a concentration of 35 mg ml⁻¹. To remove contaminants the dispersion was exfoliated by horn-probe ultrasonication (Sonics Vibra-cell VCX-750 ultrasonic processor) for 1 h at an amplitude of 55%, with a pulse rate of 6 s on 2 s off. The resulting dispersion was centrifuged (Hettich Mikro 220 R) for 1 h at 6000 RPM. The resulting sediment was redispersed in IPA. This dispersion was then exfoliated by ultrasonication at an amplitude of 55%, with a pulse rate of 4 s on 4 s off, for 8 hours. The resulting dispersion was separated into different size fractions by liquid cascade centrifugation (LCC).²⁶ To remove unexfoliated material from the dispersion, it was centrifuged at 500 RPM for 2 h, the sediment was discarded, and the supernatant was centrifuged at 750 RPM for 2 h. The sediment was redispersed in IPA and the supernatant was centrifuged again at 1000 RPM for 2 h. This process was repeated at 1250 RPM, 1500 RPM, 2000 RPM, 2500 RPM, 3000 RPM, 4000 RPM and 6000 RPM. The size sedimented at 750 RPM was further separated into 2 sizes by centrifuging the resulting dispersion at 500 RPM for 1 h and redispersing the sediment in IPA. All centrifugation steps were carried out at 10 °C.

Nanosheet characterisation

UV-Vis optical spectroscopy (Perkin Elmer 1050 spectrophotometer) was performed to determine the WS₂ ink concentration.⁴⁵ Inks were diluted to a suitable optical density and extinction spectra were recorded in 2 nm increments using a 4 mm quartz cuvette. Extinction and absorption spectra were measured.

A Renishaw Qontor Raman system, equipped with a 532 nm laser was used to study the compression-induced stress transfer within networks. The power of the laser was kept under ~1 mW to avoid damage on the sample. The exposure time was 10 s. 20 spectra at different spots throughout each network, both before and after compression, were collected to obtain statistically significant results. All Raman spectra were fitted to a Lorentzian.

For AFM analysis the inks were diluted to optical densities <0.1 at 300 nm in IPA and a drop of dispersion (15 µL) was flash evaporated on pre-heated (175 °C) Si/SiO₂ wafers. After deposition, the wafers were rinsed with ~15 mL of DI water and ~15 mL of IPA and dried with

compressed nitrogen. Images were captured using a Bruker Multimode 8 scanning probe microscope operated in ScanAsyst mode (noncontact) under ambient conditions, using aluminium-coated silicon cantilevers (OLTESPA-R3). 90 - 160 nanosheets were measured for each size to obtain statistically significant data. Images were captured at 1024 lines per image with a scan speed of 0.4 Hz, and $10 \times 10 \mu\text{m}$ or $20 \times 20 \mu\text{m}$ scans were acquired, depending on the size of the nanosheets.

Network deposition

Networks were deposited by spray-coating of the WS_2 inks at a concentration of 0.5 mg ml^{-1} (for the sample used for impedance spectroscopy an ink concentration of 1 mg ml^{-1} was used to produce a sufficiently thick film) onto a PET substrate coated in Al_2O_3 (Mitsubishi Paper Mills) to improve its wettability. Before network deposition interdigitated Cr/Au (3/50 nm) electrodes were deposited onto the substrate (Temescal FC2000 metal evaporation system) using stainless steel masks designed in house. Size-selected inks were spray coated using a Harder and Steenbeck Infinity airbrush attached to a computer-controlled Janome JR2300N mobile gantry. A N_2 back pressure of 45 psi, nozzle diameter of 0.4 mm and stand-off distance of 100 mm between the nozzle and substrate were used.⁴⁶ The networks were deposited onto substrates heated to $80 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and the dimensions of the printed trace were controlled using a stainless steel mask.

Network compression

The deposited networks were compressed (Specac Atlas 15T hydraulic press) between two cylindrical metal dies. Preliminary measurements (see SI) showed the largest pressure-induced change in electrical properties to occur for an applied resistance of 200 MPa. In addition, it was found that holding the pressure for either one or two minutes resulted in very little change in electrical resistance ratio. Thus, the networks were compressed at a pressure of 200 MPa for 60 s at room temperature. Under this scenario, the compression length (width of die) to film thickness aspect ratio was very high and the strain near-uniaxial strain, giving a high (3:1 or greater) hydrostatic to shear ratio of the compression.

Optical profilometry

During the network deposition process, a glass slide was placed beside the PET substrate so that the network thickness could be accurately measured. Film thickness measurements of networks spray coated onto glass slides were carried out using a Filmetrics Profilm3D Optical

Profiler. This instrument was operated in the white light interferometry (WLI) mode, with a 50× Nikon DI objective lens. The instrument was calibrated using a 50 nm gold film deposited on an Si/SiO₂, with a step-height confirmed using AFM. The 3D profiles of the samples were processed using the ProfilmOnline software. Profiles were initially levelled using a three-point level. Step-heights between the substrate and the top surface of the film were determined using the histogram step-height function. This outputs a histogram of the step height at each pixel, from which two peaks can be determined corresponding to the substrate and the top surface of the film.

SEM, FIB-SEM nt and image analysis

Scanning electron microscopy of the network surfaces was performed using a Carl ZEISS Ultra Plus SEM at an accelerating voltage of 2 kV (5 mm working distance, 30 μm aperture, SE2 detector). Compressed network thickness was calculated from FIB-SEM cross-sections (dual beam Carl ZEISS Auriga), a tungsten pad was deposited on top of the networks to protect them and the network was milled with a 240 pA ion beam, images were captured at 2 kV (5 mm working distance, 30 μm aperture, SE2 detector).

FIB-SEM nt was carried out using ZEISS ATLAS 5 software (Version 5.3.3.31). A 20 × 15 μm tungsten pad was deposited on the network surface, lines of a known geometry were etched into the surface, these lines were filled with platinum and more tungsten was deposited on top.⁴⁷ The cross-sections were sliced with a 600 pA gallium ion beam and the cross-section faced was imaged with a 2 kV electron beam (5 mm working distance, 30 μm aperture, SE2 detector).

The produced images were aligned in Dragonfly and segmented into nanosheet, pore, tungsten top pad and substrate using the Weka trainable image segmentation plugin in FIJI.^{48,49} Network porosity was calculated in FIJI,⁴⁹ tortuosity factor was calculated using taufactor³³ and the surface roughness was calculated using bespoke code.

Room temperature electrical measurements

IV curves were measured (Keithley 4200A-SCS Parameter Analyzer) for each of the samples at 5 different channel lengths between 50-150 μm and a fixed channel width of 0.02015 m. Impedance spectroscopy was carried out using a Keysight E4990E, with a test fixture (16047E) and spring-loaded gold probes to contact the sample. Measurements were carried out in

potentiostatic mode at a voltage of 50 mV, with a frequency range of 20 Hz to 30 MHz, at a precision speed of 5.

Temperature dependent electrical measurements

Temperature dependent electrical measurements were carried out using a Nextron MPS-LN system to control the device temperature. IV curves were obtained from networks with a channel length of 50 μm and a channel width of 0.02015 m using a Keithley 4200A-SCS Parameter Analyzer.

Figures

Figure 1: Characterisation of liquid phase exfoliated WS₂ nanosheets. A) Extinction spectra of size-selected nanosheets of various fractions. Inset: Typical Raman spectrum for the WS₂ nanosheets used in this work. B-C) Histograms showing data for nanosheet length (B) and thickness (C) for a typical size-selected fraction (2 krpm, 209 rad/s). D) Product of mean nanosheet length, l_{NS} , and thickness, t_{NS} , plotted versus inverse square of the angular speed of the rotor. E) Mean nanosheet length versus mean nanosheet thickness plotted versus size-selected fractions. F and G) Mean nanosheet thickness and mean nanosheet length, both plotted versus inverse angular speed of the rotor. The lines in D-F are fits to exfoliation and centrifugation equations as described in the text.

Figure 2: Characterising the effects of compression of nanosheet networks. A-B) Comparison of surface (top) and cross-sectional (bottom) SEM images of spray-deposited WS₂ networks before (A) and after (B) compression. C) Fractional thickness change after compression (termed compression ratio) plotted versus the length of the nanosheets comprising each network. D) Position of A_{1g} Raman peak before and after compression plotted versus the length of the nanosheets comprising each network. The nanosheet lengths in C and D are those calculated from the model-based scaling relationships in Figure 1 (see table S1).

Figure 3: Characterising network morphology via nano-tomography based 3D imaging. A-B) 3D images of a network of size-selected WS₂ nanosheets (2 krpm, 209 rad/s) before (A) and after (B) compression. C-E) Surface roughness (C), tortuosity factor (D), and porosity (E) values extracted from 3D images before and after compression and plotted versus nanosheet size. F) Morphology scaling factor plotted versus nanosheet size for uncompressed and compressed states.

compressed networks. The lines are empirical power law fits. The nanosheet lengths in C-F are those calculated from the model-based scaling relationships in Figure 1 (see table S1).

Figure 4: Electrical properties of uncompressed and compressed WS_2 networks. A) Measured electrical conductivity for size-selected networks before and after compression. B) Ratio of the post- and pre-compression network conductivity as a function of nanosheet size, l_{NS} . C-D) Network conductivity (on log scale), corrected for morphological factors, plotted versus nanosheet size for networks before (C) and after (D) compression. The solid lines are fits to Equation 2. E-F) Network conductivity, before and after compression for a network of 2 krpm nanosheets, plotted versus both temperature (E) and inverse temperature (F). The lines in F show activated behaviour. The nanosheet lengths in A-D are those calculated from the model-based scaling relationships in Figure 1 (see table S1).

Figure 5: Impedance characterisation of a compressed WS₂ network. A-B) Real (A) and imaginary (B) impedance spectra measured for different channel lengths, L_{Ch} , on a size-selected WS₂ network ($I_{NS} = 594$ nm). The solid lines are fits to an equivalent circuit (A, inset) model described by Equations 4-5. C-E) Values of equivalent circuit parameters, R_s (C), R_p (D) and C_p (E), plotted versus channel length. The solid lines are fits to equations 6-8.

Supporting Information: Table of nanosheet dimensions; figures showing nanosheet dimensions; effect of pressure on electrical properties of networks; more detailed data fitting information.

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